

Education Quarterly Reviews

Poonvichaen, J., & Sutheejariyawat, P. (2022). Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(3), 231-245.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.03.541

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills

Jirasak Poonvichaen¹, Phrakru Sutheejariyawat²

¹ Mahamakut Buddhist University, Isan Campus, Thailand. E-mail: jirasak25223@gmail.com

² Mahamakut Buddhist University, Isan Campus, Thailand. E-mail: sakorn2514@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aimed at strengthening the visionary leadership skills of students through Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology, which is a spiral cycle of Planning, Acting, Observing, and Reflecting (PAOR). In this study, the researchers conducted this investigation over the course of two cycles (each lasting one semester) in the Academic Year of 2021. The three expected outcomes of the development were as follows: 1) there would be changes from both anticipated and unanticipated practices; 2) the learning would be obtained from the practices at the research level, the group level (co-researchers), and at the organizational level (school); and 3) there would be knowledge gained from the practices in the specific context of Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School (the research area). There were 12 teachers, who were the co-researchers, and 425 students, who comprised the target group for the development. The research results contributed to the anticipated changes. In other words, the students had higher average scores from the visionary leadership skills assessment results when the 3 phases were compared (before and after the 1st cycle and after the 2nd cycle). In addition, the co-researchers and the students were exposed to unanticipated effects. In addition, the research team, the co-researchers, and the school also learned the lessons from the practice considered as the knowledge, which is a model called Six Driving Forces that Affect the Success of the Project entitled 'Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills.'

Keywords: Visionary Leadership Skills, Participatory Action Research, Participation, Democratic Leadership

1. Introduction

Visionary leadership skills are important for several reasons as follows: 1) knowing the purpose and working approaches is important to accomplishing the desired success; 2) individuals can be inspired to work in order to achieve goals; 3) explanations can be given for what is happening in the present as a reason for making a decision about the vision of the future; 4) perspectives can be broadened without sticking to the unnecessary details; 5) regarding situations, individuals can be reminded that no matter how difficult a situation is, the ultimate goal, which has been previously set will remain unchanged; 6) individuals can be empowered to have the courage to take risks and turn those risks into opportunities in order to achieve the highest goals; 7) individuals can gain an understanding of learning, which promotes the development of personal skills and the ability to make effective decisions; 9) efforts can be undertaken to find better and faster ways to achieve success; 10) individuals can be encouraged to undertake self-exploration and to express the attitudes of visionary leadership; and 11) individuals

can be inspired to take on change and to solve internal problems (Achieve, Center for Leadership, n.d.; Akbarzadeh, n.d.; Kinsey, 2018; and Wroblewski, 2019).

There are some interesting statements about the concepts of leadership and visionary leadership. Some examples are as follows: "Everyone can be a leader. Everyone has the potential to be a leader when they use their ability to influence and take action." (Patulli, 2018); "Education is the mother of leadership." - *Wendell Willkie*"; "Leadership and learning are indispensable to each other." - *John F. Kennedy* (Kruse, 2012); "Without strong visionary leadership, no strategy will be executed effectively." - *Robert S. Kaplan*; and "When the world is in the midst of change, when adversity and opportunity are almost indistinguishable, this is the time for visionary leadership and when leaders need to look beyond the survival needs of those they're serving." - *Chip Conley* (AzQuotes, n.d.). Some researchers have explained the characteristics of visionary leadership skills. Kinsey (2018) stated that the 15 characteristics of these skills consisted of the following: 1) being detail-oriented and aware, 2) being innovative, 3) having conviction, 4) being determined, 5) being persistent, 6) being an excellent communicator, 7) having strategic thinking, 8) being dedicated, 9) being humble, 10) being empowered, 11) being service-oriented, 12) being growth-oriented, 13) being ethical, 14) being caring, and 15) being inspiring. Moreover, Schine (n.d.) mentioned that the 10 characteristics of visionary leadership skills were as follows: 1) being innovative, 2) being persistent, 3) being willing to take risks, 4) being organized, 5) being enthusiastic, 6) staying focused, 7) being willing to listen to others, 8) having charisma, 9) having a sense of responsibility, and 10) being optimistic. In addition, others articulated attitudes towards visionary leadership skills. For instance, Indeed Career Guide (2020) stated four guidelines for visionary leadership: 1) define your vision, 2) create a sense of purpose, 3) motivate your team, and 4) adjust your goals as needed. Furthermore, Anyado (2012), a UK based multiple award-winning Global Leadership Speaker, Corporate Trainer, Futurist, and Author stated that there were five steps to developing visionary leadership skills: 1) leading with excellence; 2) seeing what others do not see; 3) achieving in the present, but planning for the future; 4) positively impacting different generations; and 5) raising up other visionaries.

In accordance with the importance of visionary leadership skills, the concepts of "Everyone can be a leader" and "Education is the mother of leadership.", and the approaches to developing visionary leadership skills, the research team was inspired to carry out the project, "Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills," for the students of Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School, at which the first researcher was the Director of the school. The research was conducted utilizing Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology, in which the researcher and co-researchers participated and collaborated with equal status in the process of Planning, Acting, Observing, and Reflecting (PAOR) in a continuous spiral cycle, which focused on making sustainable changes due to the obligation to what had been created at all stages of participation.

2. Research Objectives

This research aimed at strengthening the visionary leadership skills of the students of Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School through the methodology of Participatory Action Research (PAR). The three expected outcomes of the development were as follows: 1) there would be changes from both anticipated and unanticipated practices; 2) learning would be obtained from the practice at the researcher level, the group level (co-researchers), and at the organizational level (school); and 3) the knowledge gained from the practice would be used as a theoretical foundation in the specific context of Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School.

3. Literature Review

Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology was employed in this research, which focused on a review of the literature. The goal was to obtain more theoretical suggestions on a wide range of issues and perspectives, which the researchers could present to the co-researchers, and which could contribute to the co-researchers by helping them to gain knowledge and to develop an understanding of how to best integrate the suggestions in accordance with their prior knowledge and experiences. This created a stronger power of development commensurate with the following principle: "Practice without additional theories is like a blind person, who can't

go far, but (who) continues using the same old methods.” The research team, therefore, studied the theoretical perspectives on the following 6 issues:

- 1) The definitions of visionary leadership skills were derived from: Eden Project (n.d.), Jeffrey (n.d.), Kinsey (2018), Lucas (2021), Meier (n.d.), Status Net (n.d.), and Team Technology (n.d.).
- 2) The significance of visionary leadership skills was derived from the attitudes of: Achieve, Center for Leadership (n.d.), Akbarzadeh (n.d.), Kinsey (2018), and Wroblewski (2019).
- 3) The characteristics of visionary leadership skills were derived from the attitudes of: Cecere (2014), Cecere (2015), Cedricj (2017), Dream Achievers Academy (n.d.), Ginger Leadership Communications (2017), Jeffrey (n.d.), Kinsey (2018), Setzer (2014), and Status Net (n.d.).
- 4) The developmental approaches to visionary leadership skills were derived from the attitudes of: Altman (2016), Anyado (2012), Constantino (2017), Indeed Career Guide (2020), McMinn (n.d.), Meinert (2015), Taylor (2017), and Work Front (2018).
- 5) The procedures of the development of visionary leadership skills were derived from the attitudes of: Adams (2013), Kerr (2014), McMinn (n.d.), Northwest Executive Education (2020), Orr (2018), and Williams (n.d.).
- 6) The assessment of visionary leadership skills was derived from the attitudes of: Dhammika (n.d.), Gilley (2005), and Simons and Abramms (1996).

Considering the results of the literature review, which were related to the six issues previously mentioned, the researchers determined that the perspectives on the developmental approaches (principles / concepts / techniques / methods / activities) had been important knowledge because it had allowed the co-researchers to understand the various developmental approaches that can enable “Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills.” to become more effectively utilized. As a result, the researchers were able to present 41 developmental guidelines (principles / concepts / techniques / methods / activities), which were derived from a synthesis of the viewpoints of the cited scholars. Each guideline serves to empower teachers to motivate students to perform the following actions:

- 1) think the unthinkable
- 2) understand that it is not about them
- 3) play nice with others
- 4) do not think that they know it all
- 5) have the right mindset
- 6) visualize the future
- 7) study the past
- 8) see yourself
- 9) see things early
- 10) connect the dots
- 11) initiate the process of crafting vision
- 12) invent alternate “pictures of the future” and choose the best
- 13) submit all potential vision to robust dialogue
- 14) write the vision down
- 15) allow vision to mature
- 16) communicate the vision
- 17) initiate the process of crafting a vision
- 18) immediately connect vision with execution
- 19) continually adjust the vision
- 20) lead with hope
- 21) talk about extraordinary goals
- 22) include things that are attainable
- 23) make certain that it has been clearly communicated
- 24) live in the present, but always look to the future
- 25) always seek knowledge, never stop learning
- 26) paint a clear picture for those you lead
- 27) personify the vision

- 28) welcome and encourage feedback
- 29) strive to motivate
- 30) lead with excellence
- 31) see what others do not see
- 32) achieve in the present, but plan for the future
- 33) positively impact different generations
- 34) raise up other visionaries
- 35) have a diagnostic perspective
- 36) have a perspective of innovation
- 37) have an unseen perspective
- 38) define the vision
- 39) create a sense of purpose
- 40) motivate the team
- 41) adjust goals as needed

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Types of Action Research

According to Sanrattana's analytical and synthetic study (2018) on Action Research and based upon the perspectives of Arhar, Holly, and Kasten (2001), Carr and Kemmis (1992), Coghlan and Brannick (2007), Creswell (2008), James, Milenkiewicz, and Bucknam (2008), Kemmis and McTaggart (1992), McTaggart (1991), McTaggart (2010), and Mills (2007), it was found that Action Research was first developed in 1952 by Kurt Lewin and was followed by several other scholars, such as David Kolb in 1984 and Wilfred Carr and Stephen Kemmis in 1986. Carr and Kemmis (1992) categorized action research into three levels. Firstly, in **Technical Action Research**, the key concept is that the researcher acts as an outside expert, who brings the ideas, plans, or projects that he or she has been thinking about or has developed to the co-researchers. Secondly, in **Practical Action Research**, the researcher becomes more involved with the co-researchers. Unlike Technical Action Research, the researcher's own ideas, plans, or projects are not taken, but the researcher acts as a consultant, who provides stimulation, sets the issues, and gives direction to bring about collaboration through the sharing of ideas, taking action, making observations, and reflecting upon the results. Thirdly, in **Emancipatory Action Research / Participatory Action Research**, the researcher participates in the research together with the co-researchers in a manner of collaboration in which all of them share equal status (Equality). This research was conducted utilizing Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology. According to a study by Sanrattana (2018), it is a research methodology that is based on Critical Social Theory and on the Theories of Post-modernism that places emphasis on participation in and the democratization of the actions and consequences that can contribute to changes, learning, and the body of knowledge that are obtained from the practice. It is a research methodology, in which the researcher participates in the research with the co-researchers in a manner of collaboration in which all have an equal status in Planning, Acting, Observing, and Reflecting (PAOR) as an endlessly continuous spiral cycle.

4.2 Cycles Steps and Ethics of the Study

The Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology was used as a spiral cycle in which the aforementioned steps of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting (PAOR) were repeated indefinitely. However, due to the time constraints of the course curriculum, the research team established two research cycles lasting one semester each in the Academic Year of 2021. Twelve teachers volunteered to participate, and 425 students made up the target group for development. Each step in the research cycle was carried out as follows:

Cycle1

Step 1: The preparation included 3 activities: 1) Explaining the research procedures to the co-researchers in order that the decision to participate in the research was voluntary in accordance with the Code of Conduct: "(a) the participants must be notified about the nature of the research procedures and the benefits at the beginning, and (b)

those who do not wish to participate in the research must be accepted and respected for individual rights.”; 2) Designing a collaboration practice in accordance with the research ethics: “(a) Involving the research participants in the design of the research process, and (b) having joint consultations in which suggestions are accepted by all parties.”; and 3) Learning lessons was based on the principles of “(a) analyzing, critiquing and performing self-assessment; and (b) learning from both successful and unsuccessful actions and contributing to the process of learning together in a systematic manner.”

Step 2: Planning included 4 activities: 1) the “co-researchers” brainstormed to find out “how students develop visionary leadership skills based on their knowledge and experiences in accordance with “The Principle of awareness of potential, expertise, and being a stakeholder of the community.”; 2) the approaches for theoretical development, which were based on a review of the relevant literature, were transferred to the co-researchers in response to the principle: “The research participants are able to equally access information.”; and 3) following the brainstorming, an action plan was developed to integrate the developmental approaches that the “Co-investigators jointly determine” and the “Theoretical developmental guidelines are based on the researcher’s relevant literature studies.”, which was in accordance with the principle of “Listening to the opinions of all research participants” and the Code of Conduct: “The consultation and suggestions were agreed upon by all parties.” (Note: The action plan construction resulted in 50 developmental guidelines, as shown in Tables 1.) The lessons, which were learned, were applied in accordance with the aforementioned principles.

Step 3: Taking action consisted of 4 activities: 1) The evaluation form with the implementation of alternative suggestions and the student development assessment form was constructed to assess three phases (before and after the implementation of the First Cycle and after the implementation of the Second Cycle) and was in accordance with the ethical principle of “Research direction and expected outcomes arise from joint decisions.”; 2) The conditions prior to the implementation of Cycle 1 were assessed by using the evaluation form on the practice of alternative suggestions and the student development assessment form; 3) The jointly formulated action plan was implemented based on the following principles: “(a) Specific context, (b) Multi-skills, (c) Focusing on change, (d) Focusing on action to achieve results, and (e) sustainable development” and were conducted in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “Participants influence work.”; and 4) the lessons learned were applied in accordance with the aforementioned principles.

Step 4: Observing is being aware of the collection of information from activities and practices through the use of observation forms, in-depth interview forms, group interview forms, and examining or recording forms (Examining/Record), such as journals, maps, audiotapes and videotapes, artifacts, and field notes. It is carried out in accordance with the principle of “Recording all participants involved with the activities and practices” in response to the Code of Conduct: “(1) observations or examinations of documents for other purposes must first be authorized, and (2) never infringe upon the copyright of others’ writings or views without first negotiating before publishing or disseminating.”

Step 5: Reflection consisted of 3 activities: 1) assessing the current condition after the implementation of the first cycle by using the evaluation form, which focused on the practice of making alternative suggestions and on the student development assessment form; 2) reflecting upon the performance results from the brainstorming to analyze the results of all the steps in Cycle 1 in accordance with the following principles: “(a) listening to the opinions of all research participants, (b) analyzing, critiquing, and performing self-assessment, (c) learning from both successful and unsuccessful actions, and contributing to a jointly systematic learning process” and in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “Performance will remain visible and allow others to give feedback.”; and 3) identifying the lessons, which had been learned, was based on the aforementioned principles.

The researchers used Kurt Lewin’s Force-Field Analysis (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2000) to examine the following: 1) what the former conditions had been like, 2) what the expected outcomes had been, 3) what the driving forces that were used to bring about change had been, 4) how much of that driving force had led to the expected change, 5) what anti-changes had been made, and 6) what guidelines had been suggested from the anti-changes to increase the powerful drive and/or to reduce or to remove the anti-changes in the performance, which may involve the

following: a) improving the efficiency of the existing drive in order to make it more efficient, b) adding new drive power that is more effective, or c) both improving the existing drive power and adding the new drive power.

Cycle 2

Step 6: Planning consisted of 2 activities: 1) creating the action plan and 2) taking the lessons learned.

Step 7: Taking action consisted of 2 activities: 1) Implementing the action plan from Step 6 and 2) taking the lessons learned.

Step 8: Observing refers to taking note of the collection of information from various activities by using the observation form, the in-depth interview form, the group interview form, or an examining/recording form (Examining/Record) as conducted in Cycle 1.

Step 9: Reflecting consisted of the 3 following activities: 1) assessing the current conditions after the implementation of the second Cycle by using the evaluation form on the practice of giving alternative suggestions and the student development assessment form, 2) reflecting on the performance results from brainstorming to consider the results of every step of the second Cycle; and 3) embracing the lessons learned.

Step 10: The Conclusion of the Research was marked by holding workshops together for both the researcher and the co-researchers. The results were derived from the observations, the lessons learned, the three phases of the current condition assessment (before and after the implementation of the First Cycle and after the implementation of the Second Cycle), the evaluation form on the practice of alternative suggestions, the student development assessment and from the results from the reflections in Step 5 and Step 9. All were summarized as the research results according to the following principles: “(1) specific contexts; (2) listening to the opinions from all the research participants; (3) analysis, critiques, and self-assessments; (4) Learning from both successful and unsuccessful actions by bringing about a jointly systematic learning process;” and (5) being in accordance with the Code of Conduct: (a) “Consultation and suggestions are agreed upon by all parties, and (b) the performance results will remain visible and allow others to make suggestions.”

4.3 Research site and research participants

The areas of research were chosen based on convenience, the potential of the research team, and the possibility of obtaining cooperation from the co-researchers from Phayakkhaphumwittayakan School, where the first researcher is the Director of the school. Following the activities, the research procedures were explained to 12 volunteer co-researchers (school teachers), and 425 students, who were the target group for development.

4.4 Research tools

- 1) **The tools for collecting data from all the activities:** To consider the appropriateness and the situations, the research team considered using the following tools based on the concept of Mills (2007): 1) an observation form, 2) an in-depth interview form and group interview form, and 3) an Examining or recording form (Examining/Record) (i.e., journals, maps, audiotapes and videotapes, artifacts, and field notes, etc.).
- 2) **The co-researchers’ practice level assessment form:** The researcher and co-researchers jointly constructed a self-assessment form to assess the co-researchers’ practice level in 3 phases (before and after the practice in Cycle 1 and after the practice in Cycle 2). It was designed with a 5-level rating scale (mostly agree, agree, moderate, disagree, and mostly disagree). However, in terms of content validity (IOC: Indexes of Item-Objective Congruence), this assessment form was not approved by the experts nor was it tried out with the sample group to find the Alpha Coefficient of Reliability because the questions in the assessment were “Developmental Guidelines” that had been the joint intentions of the researcher and the co-researchers and had been the results of brainstorming to integrate the “Developmental

Guidelines jointly determined by the co-researchers” and the “Theoretical development guidelines based on the results from the researcher's relevant literature study” from the Action Plan activities of Cycle 1.

- 3) **Visionary leadership skills assessment of students:** The researcher and the co-researchers jointly constructed the results of studies indicating the characteristics of visionary leadership skills from the perspectives of Cecere (2014), Cecere (2015), Cedricj (2017), Dream. Achievers Academy (n.d.), Ginger Leadership Communications (2017), Jeffrey (n.d.), Kinsey (2018), Setzer (2014), and Status Net (n.d.) and from studies that examined the concept of the assessment of visionary leadership skills by Dhammika (n.d.), Gilley (2005), and Simons and Abramms (1996). A self-assessment form was used for the students, who were a target group of the development. It was a 5-level rating scale form (mostly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, mostly disagree). There were 30 questions in total. The assessment form was reviewed for the Indices of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC), which was consistent with the perspectives of Rovinelli and Hambleton (1977). In addition, the form was examined by 5 experts in the fields of the educational administration and educational measurement. It was discovered that all questions had exhibited an IOC value of greater than the specified threshold of 0.50, which indicated that the questions in this assessment had been consistent with the development's objectives or expectations (Chachanawirote & Vantum, 2017). Furthermore, Cronbach's method was used to analyze the Alpha Coefficient of Confidence with 30 students from a school that was not in the research area (Buayaipittayakom School). It was discovered that the overall Alpha Coefficient of Reliability had been 0.93 and had been classified as follows: ‘My visionary aspect’ had been 0.79, ‘My visionary leader's attribute’ had been 0.70, ‘My visionary leader's habit’ had been 0.88, and ‘My commitment to being an excellent visionary leader’ had been 0.86. All of these had been equal to or higher than 0.70 (UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group, 2016).

4.5 Data Collection and Analysis

In accordance with the principle of "There is a record of all participants of their activities and practice," the researchers and co-researchers played a role in data collection at every step by using the aforementioned tools. Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were used to analyze the quantitative data from the two self-assessment forms. In addition, observations, interviews, and recordings were used to collect qualitative data. The process of data analysis was as follows: 1) the integrity of the data was checked to examine whether or not it had met the desired objectives; 2) the reliability of the data was verified in order to examine whether or not it had matched the actual situation by comparing the results of the recording of each participant with the recording results from the other forms of data collection; and 3) the data was presented in the form of Thick and Critical Description through story-telling based on a Factual and Neutral Manner. The descriptive evidence consisted of numbers, statistics, tables, graphics, photographs, direct quotes (verbatim), or the informant's improvised dialogue, which indicated feelings and viewpoints on the same issue, and which may have supported or contradicted each other.

5. Results

5.1. Changes

5.1.1. Anticipated Changes

By following the implementation of the project "Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Students' Visionary Leadership Skills" for students at Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School, the researchers and co-researchers had two expectations as follows: 1) there would be greater changes in the co-researchers' practice given the results of the three comparative assessment phases (before and after the First Cycle, and after the Second Cycle); and 2) there would be greater changes in the students' visionary leadership skills based on the results of the three comparative assessment phases (before and after the First Cycle, and after the Second Cycle).

The First Expectation: The total mean was found to be 2.32, 3.09, and 4.43, respectively, based on the assessment of the degree of adoption of the developmental guidelines (principles / concepts / techniques / methods / activities) in three phases (before and after the implementation of the First Cycle and after the implementation of the Second Cycle), which indicated that when seeking to enhance the visionary leadership skills of students, the co-researchers had more actively utilized the developmental alternatives. The findings from both the overall analyses and the discrete data analyses are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: A comparison of the results of the assessment with regard to the implementation of the developmental guidelines in the 3 phases (before and after the implementation of the first Cycle and after the implementation of the second Cycle)

Developmental Guidelines (Principles / Concept / Techniques / Methods / Activities)	Assessment results from the Pre-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.
1) Students are given self-confidence.	3.17	0.58	3.33	0.49	4.50	0.67
2) Students are given the courage to make decisions and to take responsibility.	2.58	0.79	3.25	0.45	4.42	0.51
3) Teachers organize activities to make students into leaders with ethical visions.	2.08	0.67	2.67	0.78	5.00	0.00
4) Teachers provide a classroom environment that is conducive to the development of visionary leadership.	2.25	0.75	3.17	0.72	4.42	0.79
5) Students are provided with a wide range of language proficiency.	2.58	0.79	3.25	0.62	4.33	0.65
6) Students are provided with technological knowledge and skills.	2.42	0.90	2.83	0.83	4.17	0.58
7) Students are enabled to discover their own visionary leadership.	2.42	0.90	3.08	0.79	4.42	0.51
8) Teachers investigate the students' readiness and differences with individual analysis.	2.42	0.90	3.17	0.72	4.33	0.49
9) Teachers organize the activities for students to integrate different ideas.	2.00	0.74	2.58	0.79	4.17	0.94
10) Students are empowered to think the unthinkable.	2.08	0.79	2.83	0.58	4.33	0.49
11) Students are taught to know what should be avoided.	2.67	0.49	3.33	0.49	4.75	0.45
12) Students are taught to create a friendly atmosphere with others.	2.50	0.67	3.33	0.78	4.25	1.06
13) Students are taught not to assume that others know everything.	2.08	0.90	3.00	0.60	4.75	0.45
14) Students are taught to think carefully.	2.25	0.75	3.33	0.89	4.67	0.65
15) Students are taught to visualize the future.	2.17	0.72	3.17	0.58	4.83	0.39
16) Students are taught to study the past.	2.00	0.60	2.92	0.67	4.17	0.72
17) Students are enabled to analyze information by themselves.	2.75	0.87	3.42	0.51	4.42	0.51
18) Students are enabled to take a notice at an early stage.	2.42	0.67	3.00	0.60	4.25	0.87
19) Students are enabled to connect the dots.	2.42	0.67	3.08	0.51	4.83	0.39
20) Students are enabled to initiate the process of crafting a vision.	2.25	0.87	2.92	0.90	4.92	0.29
21) Students are enabled to invent 'Pictures of the Future' and choose the best.	2.08	0.67	3.25	0.45	4.17	0.94
22) Students are taught to be straightforward.	2.58	0.67	3.33	0.78	4.75	0.45
23) Students are taught to write down their visions in their notebooks.	2.25	0.75	3.00	0.60	4.75	0.45
24) Students are enabled to develop and grow their visions as much as they can.	2.08	0.90	2.92	0.51	3.83	0.58
25) Students are enabled to communicate their visions.	2.08	0.51	2.67	0.78	4.33	0.49

Developmental Guidelines (Principles / Concept / Techniques / Methods / Activities)	Assessment results from the Pre-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.	$\bar{\chi}$	S.D.
26) Students are enabled to initiate the process of crafting their visions.	2.17	0.94	3.17	0.72	4.50	0.52
27) Students are enabled to connect to their visions by immediately taking action.	2.17	0.72	3.17	0.72	4.42	0.51
28) Students are allowed to adjust their visions at any time.	2.08	0.67	3.00	0.74	4.33	0.49
29) Students are enabled to become promising team leaders.	2.42	0.67	3.17	0.72	4.50	0.52
30) Students are allowed to talk about extraordinary goals.	2.33	0.49	2.92	0.51	4.17	0.39
31) Students are enabled to set achievable goals.	2.00	0.74	3.08	0.67	4.25	0.45
32) Students are enabled to be confident in communicating clearly.	2.33	0.49	2.92	0.79	5.00	0.00
33) Students are enabled to live in the present moment, but to look to the future.	1.92	0.90	2.75	0.75	4.33	0.49
34) Students are enabled to consistently seek knowledge and never stop learning.	2.83	0.39	3.42	0.51	4.42	0.51
35) Students are enabled to show a clear and reliable image of being a team leader.	2.17	0.72	2.75	0.45	4.17	0.39
36) Students are allowed to question and to express their visions on their own.	2.25	0.75	3.08	0.51	4.33	0.49
37) Students are enabled to welcome suggestions.	2.50	0.52	3.25	0.75	4.17	0.58
38) Students are enabled to show commitment.	1.83	0.72	3.00	0.85	4.33	0.49
39) Students are enabled to become a leader with their abilities.	2.33	0.89	3.08	0.79	4.50	0.52
40) Students are enabled to see what others do not see.	2.58	0.79	2.92	0.29	4.33	0.49
41) Students are enabled to become successful in the present and to plan the future.	2.00	0.74	3.08	0.51	4.42	0.51
42) Students are enabled to produce positive results that impact different generations of people.	2.83	0.72	3.25	0.45	4.33	0.65
43) Students are enabled to increase the vision of others.	2.67	0.49	3.25	0.45	4.42	0.51
44) Students are enabled to have analytical perspectives	2.00	0.60	2.92	0.79	4.25	0.45
45) Students are enabled to have innovative perspectives.	2.50	0.67	3.33	0.49	4.50	0.52
46) Students are enabled to have perspectives that others cannot see.	2.42	0.90	3.25	0.62	4.42	0.51
47) Students are allowed to define their own visions.	1.92	0.67	3.17	0.72	4.33	0.49
48) Students are enabled to build rigid adherence to the goals.	2.33	0.78	3.08	0.67	4.17	0.58
49) Students are enabled to build motivation for the team	2.50	0.80	3.33	0.89	4.83	0.39
50) Students are allowed to adjust their goals if needed.	2.50	0.67	3.25	0.45	4.25	0.75
Total	2.32	0.27	3.09	0.11	4.43	0.20

Note: The standard deviation value was low in all 3 phases, indicating that the opinions of the assessors in each of the phases had had a low variance.

The second anticipated case: From the results of the assessment of visionary leadership skills of the students in the 3 phases, it was found that the overall average had been higher (an average of 2.64 in the pre-practice of Cycle 1, an average of 3.69 after the post-practice of Cycle 1, and an average of 4.52 after the post-practice in Cycle 2). This indicated that the development had brought about better changes, in accordance with the results of the analyses from the overall data, the aspects, and the items as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: A comparison of the results of the students' visionary leadership skills assessment in the 3 phases: before and after the First Cycle and after the Second Cycle.

The characteristics of the anticipated visionary leadership skills	Assessment results from the Pre-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 1		Assessment results from the Post-practice in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.
The desired visionary characteristics	2.70	0.54	3.64	0.57	4.49	0.40
1) Being a strategic thinker	2.82	0.61	3.36	0.67	4.30	0.57
2) Being committed	2.53	0.73	3.70	0.70	4.56	0.51
3) Creating positive energy	2.68	0.74	3.70	0.85	4.52	0.60
4) Being creative	2.69	0.73	3.62	0.70	4.51	0.52
5) Focusing on the overview	2.79	0.81	3.84	0.72	4.66	0.49
6) Being open-minded and appreciating new ideas	2.58	0.85	3.99	0.79	4.69	0.48
7) Being able to communicate in an excellent manner	2.76	0.78	3.30	0.87	4.19	0.67
8) Being meticulous and having awareness	2.78	0.76	3.60	0.71	4.49	0.54
The characteristics of a visionary leader	2.70	0.50	3.50	0.59	4.39	0.43
9) Loving innovation and new things	2.81	0.62	3.55	0.77	4.40	0.53
10) Being flexible	2.75	0.62	3.45	0.72	4.36	0.58
11) Having manageable skills	2.84	0.72	3.50	0.72	4.42	0.57
12) Having the courage to wisely take risks	2.65	0.81	3.55	0.75	4.45	0.59
13) Having emotional intelligence	2.76	0.81	3.62	0.76	4.49	0.57
14) Getting strong attention from people	2.54	0.72	3.37	0.86	4.26	0.67
15) Being service-minded	2.64	0.61	3.55	0.80	4.44	0.60
16) Loving to ask questions	2.58	0.73	3.41	0.94	4.29	0.69
The habits of a visionary leader	2.65	0.57	3.68	0.58	4.53	0.39
17) Having a clear vision and goals.	2.84	0.69	3.72	0.78	4.54	0.54
18) Performing pro-active work	2.68	0.66	3.61	0.76	4.47	0.56
19) Prioritizing work effectively	2.52	0.99	3.74	0.73	4.58	0.52
20) Utilizing the efficiency of team performance	2.71	0.78	3.75	0.72	4.61	0.53
21) Focusing on continuous learning	2.60	0.85	3.67	0.69	4.57	0.50
22) Having a strong desire for new information	2.55	0.89	3.58	0.78	4.43	0.55
23) Building working relationships between different work groups.	2.57	0.85	3.88	0.85	4.65	0.53
A commitment to leadership with a great vision	2.52	0.64	4.08	0.81	4.74	0.47
24) Taking into account the opportunity	2.67	0.97	3.87	0.71	4.67	0.47
25) Being a good colleague	2.35	1.09	4.11	0.75	4.78	0.43
26) Accepting failure in order to move forward	2.39	0.96	3.95	0.79	4.68	0.50
27) Having a broad perspective about situations	2.41	0.93	3.85	0.78	4.64	0.53
28) Trying to work outside of the old framework	2.56	0.99	3.74	0.74	4.58	0.54
29) Accepting the unknown and learning to ask for help	2.66	0.89	4.00	0.68	4.77	0.42
30) Keeping an open mind with regard to changes	2.53	0.92	4.08	0.81	4.74	0.47
Total	2.64	0.49	3.69	0.52	4.52	0.35

Note - The standard deviation value was low in all 3 phases, indicating that the opinions of the assessors in each phase had had a low variance.

5.1.2. Unanticipated changes

In addition to the anticipated changes, this research contributed to unanticipated changes in the following positive ways:

1. The co-researchers were actively involved in this research, especially during the discussions about the research techniques. In addition, they were interested in asking questions, in providing suggestions, and in giving a summary of the guidelines for the practice.

2. The co-researchers explored the theoretical concepts of some academics and academic officials until they understood the concepts. Then they took the creative initiative to enhance their students' visionary leadership skills.
3. The co-researchers shared their expertise within the team, which led to a better understanding of the success of the work compared to when each of them had worked independently in the past.
4. The researchers and the co-researchers exchanged knowledge, issues, obstacles, and solutions through their discussions, which were crystallized into guidelines for further practice.
5. Within the group, a positive work atmosphere and a sense of sincerity were created. In order to achieve quality and successful work, the principles of teachings in Buddhism were applied by fostering goodwill, generosity, and support for one another.
6. By utilizing the Active Learning model, students learned from real practice, which resulted in teamwork, the courage to express ideas, analytical and synthetic skills, communication, and the exchange of knowledge within the team, self-confidence when presenting, and visionary leadership with integrity.

5.2. Learning by practice

As specified by the project "Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills," which was conducted for the students in Phayakkhaphum Wittayakarn School over the course of 2 semesters in the Academic Year 2021, both the researchers, the co-researchers, and the school learned from the many practices.

Regarding this research article, the most important collaborative learning consisted of the following: 1) the working methods, which should be assessed to examine the current situation before the practice; 2) a realization of the importance of exchanging knowledge within the team, which would result in success and in better work results than when working independently; 3) the application of Buddhist teachings to serve as a reminder to work with the goal of achieving results; and 4) an enhancement of the visionary leadership skills of students, by placing emphasis upon the following: a) teaching and learning in an active learning style, b) assisting students have the courage to express their thoughts, c) building analytical and synthetic skills, d) working as a team, e) communicating and exchanging knowledge within the team, and f) developing the ability to present ideas with confidence.

5.3. Knowledge gained from the practice

The project, "Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Students' Visionary Leadership Skills," was conducted for the students at Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School over the course of two semesters in the Academic Year 2021. It generated grounded-theory knowledge from field collaboration according to Kurt Lewin's Force-Field Analysis framework, which was employed in this research. It is a body of knowledge that serves as a reminder that priorities must be assessed in order to determine the following: 1) what the previous conditions are in any work or development, 2) what the expectations are, 3) what the driving force to bring about change is, 4) how much driving force it will take to make the anticipated changes, 5) what that anti-changes are that will emerge, and 6) what suggestions are available to increase the efficiency of the driving force, while lowering or even eliminating the anti-changes. The findings were then used in planning for the next cycle, which would contribute to improving the efficiency of the existing driving force, or seeking a new and more efficient drive, or possibly both.

According to the results of the assessment of the previous condition before the practice of both enhancing visionary leadership skills for students and examining the existing visionary leadership skills of the students, it was found that they were at a low level (the means were 2.32 and 2.64, respectively). Therefore, the researchers adopted the following driving forces: 1) the principles, concepts, and ethics of participatory action research (as written in the research methodology); 2) the Dharma principles that are the teachings of Buddhism; 3) the alternative academic suggestions, which were derived from the researcher's study of the relevant literature, which was supported by the suggestions that were based on the co-researchers' experiences, and which yielded 50 practical alternative suggestions; 4) the principles and strategies of teamwork, which were determined in advance of the performance;

5) an action-oriented work goal, which was set to achieve changes based on the concept: 'Change is not an Event, but a Process;' and 6) reflection on the performance to discover the anti-changes and how to best deal with them. The results of the application of the 6 important driving forces used in this research resulted in the expected changes; the co-researchers applied the developmental guidelines (principles / concepts / techniques / methods / activities), which were implemented in the phases of pre-practice and post-practice in Cycle 1 and in the post-practice phase in Cycle 2, which contributed to higher averages at 2.32, 3.09, and 4.43, respectively. Similarly, the results of the assessment of the students' visionary leadership skills were also found to have higher overall averages (2.64 in the pre-practice of Cycle 1, 3.69 in the post-practice of Cycle 1, and 4.52 in the post-practice of Cycle 2).

6. Discussion

Based on the perspective of Carr and Kemmis (1992), action research can be categorized into the three levels mentioned above: 1) Technical Action Research, 2) Practical Action Research, and 3) Emancipatory Action Research / Participatory Action Research. Regarding the project, "Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills," for students in Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School, the research team chose Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology for this research in accordance with the analytical and synthetic study conducted by Sanrattana (2018) given that the research methodology places emphasis on Democratic leadership. Cherry (2022) noted that Democratic leadership, also known as participative leadership or shared leadership, is a leadership style in which members of the group participate in decision-making processes. This type of leadership can apply to any type of organization, from private businesses to schools to the government. With a democratic leadership style, everyone is given the opportunity to participate, to freely exchange their ideas, and is encouraged to join in the discussions. While this process tends to focus on group equality and the free flow of ideas, the democratic leader is still there to offer guidance and control. The democratic leader is also charged with deciding who is in the group and who gets to contribute to the decisions that are being made. Research has found that a democratic leadership style is one of the most effective types and leads to higher productivity and better contributions from group members, as well as increases group morale.

Similarly, PhD students in the field of Educational Administration at the Isan Campus of Mahamakut Buddhist University also chose this research methodology for the following studies: "Participatory Practice "Teach Less, Learn More": A Case of Srikrakuanwittayakom School" by Roobtam and Sanrattana (2021); "Development of Learning by E-Learning System: A Case of Mahamakut Buddhist University, Mahavajiralongkorn Rajavijayalaya Campus" by Phramaha Paijit Uttamadhammo (Sakhong) and Phrakrusutheejariyawattana (2021); "Cooperative practices to enhance the quality of work-integrated learning at Nong Khai Technical College" by Sarapoom and Phrakrudhammapissamai (2021); and "Teachers and participatory action research for developing learning environments" by Thawinwong and Sanrattana (2022). Results from the studies found both anticipated and unanticipated changes. The researchers, the co-researchers, and the educational institutions learned from several important practices and this knowledge resulted in a new body of knowledge that was gained from the practices. These findings demonstrated the benefits of Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology, which can be used as the main driving force together with the initiative to use other principles, concepts, and practices to create an additional driving force. Therefore, it is a research methodology, the use of which should be supported and promoted so that any work in educational institutions or other organizations can be developed.

7. Recommendations

According to the research findings from the practices mentioned above, grounded theory from collaboration within the field of a specific local context is represented. In other words, it is not a universal theory to be referenced with other populations. However, if any educational institution is interested, it could also be used as a case study. In addition, Coghlan and Brannick (2007) and James, Milenkiewicz, and Bucknam (2008), stated that "Despite the limitations of dissemination or reference of the action research, it can be taken as a point of view or an important event that arises as a recommendation for (its) use in other similar situations or that are aiming for a similar change." Therefore, other educational institutions will be able to apply the model of *Six Driving Forces for Success*

in the project, 'Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills,' for students in Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School (as shown in Figure 1) as a case study.

Figure 1: The model of the Six Driving Forces for Success used in the project, 'Practicing Collaborative Teachers to Strengthen Student's Visionary Leadership Skills,' for students in Phayakkhaphumwittayakarn School

References

- Achieve, Center for Leadership. (n.d.). *The importance of visionary leadership*. Retrieved from <https://ca.achievecentre.com/blog/importance-visionary-leadership/>
- Adams, S. (2013, May 5). *Four steps to successful brainstorming*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/susanadams/2013/03/05/4-steps-to-successful-brainstorming/?sh=3e8c72f25992>
- Akbarzadeh, K. (n.d.). *Benefits of being visionary*. Retrieved from <https://www.dreamachieversacademy.com/visionary-benefits/>
- Altman, J. (2016, May 18). *How to be a visionary leader*. Retrieved from <https://www.bizjournals.com/bizjournals/how-to/growth-strategies/2016/03/how-to-be-a-visionary-leader.html>
- Anyado, O. (2012, October 28). *Five steps to becoming a visionary leader of distinction*. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/five-steps-becoming-visionary-leader-distinction-onyi-anyado>
- Arhar, J.M., Holly, M.L., & Kasten, W.C. (2001). *Action research for teachers*. Merrill Prentice Hall.
- AzQuotes. (n.d.). *Visionary leadership quotes*. Retrieved from <https://www.azquotes.com/quotes/topics/visionary-leadership.html>
- Carr, W. & Kemmis, S. (1992). *Becoming critical: Education, knowledge, and action research* (3rd Ed.). Falmer Press.
- Cecere, L. (2014, May 28). *Seven characteristics of a visionary*. Retrieved from <https://consumergoods.com/7-characteristics-visionary>
- Cecere, L. (2015 May 27). *Characteristics of visionaries*. Retrieved from <https://consumergoods.com/characteristics-visionaries>
- Cedricj. (2017, February 23). *Five behaviors of a visionary leader*. Retrieved from <https://cedricj.wordpress.com/2017/02/23/five-behaviors-of-a-visionary-leader/>
- Chaichanawirote U. & Vantum, C. (2017). Evaluation of content validity for research instrument. *Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences*, 11(2), 105-111.

- Cherry, K. (2022, May 23). *What Is democratic leadership?* Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-democratic-leadership-2795315#:~:text=With%20a%20democratic%20leadership%20style,to%20offer%20guidance%20and%20control.>
- Coghlan, D. & Brannick, T. (2007). *Doing action research in your own organization* (2nd Ed.). Sage.
- Constantino, T. (2017, June 15). *Three perspectives of visionary leaders.* Retrieved from <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/295808>
- Creswell, J.W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, (3rd Ed.). Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Dharmika, K.A.S. (n.d.) *Visionary leadership and organizational commitment: The mediating effect of leader member exchange (LMX).* Department of Human Resource Management University of Kelaniya SRI LANKA
- Dream Achievers Academy. (n.d.). *Seven signs of visionary leaders.* Retrieved from <https://www.dreamachieversacademy.com/visionary-signs/>
- Eden Project (n.d.). *What is visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <https://www.edenproject.com/learn/for-organisations/creative-leadership/what-is-visionary-leadership>
- Gilley, A. (2005). *The manager as change leader.* Praeger. Retrieved from <https://leap.colostate.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/24/2018/02/Dr.-Hanson-self-assessment.pdf>
- Ginger Leadership Communications. (2017, May 15). *Seven characteristics of a visionary leader.* Retrieved from <https://www.gingerleadershipcomms.com/article/7-characteristics-of-a-visionary-leader>
- Indeed Career Guide. (2020, February 14). *Your guide to visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/your-guide-to-visionary-leadership>
- James, E.A., Milenkiewicz, M.T., & Bucknam, A. (2008). *Participatory action research for educational leadership: Using data-driven decision making to improve schools.* Sage.
- Jeffrey, S (n.d.). *Visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <https://scottjeffrey.com/visionary-leadership/>
- Jeffrey, S. (n.d.). *Ten attributes of visionary leadership for change agents and outperforming entrepreneurs.* Retrieved from <https://scottjeffrey.com/visionary-leadership/>
- Kemmis, S., & McTaggart, R. (1992). *The action research planner* (3rd Ed.). Deakin University.
- Kerr, J. (2014, October 14). *Five steps for becoming a visionary leader developing these skills can improve your ability to anticipate and impact the future.* Retrieved from <https://www.inc.com/james-kerr/5-steps-to-becoming-a-visionary-leader.html>
- Kinsey, A. (2018, October 16). *What is visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <https://bizfluent.com/info-8721665-visionary-leadership.html>
- Kruse, K. (2012, October 16). *100 best quotes on leadership.* Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kevinkruse/2012/10/16/quotes-on-leadership/?sh=7b23bcd2feb8>
- Lucas, S. (2021, September 21). *Visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/visionary-leadership-4174279>
- Lunenburg, F. C. & Ornstein, A. C. (2000). *Educational administration: Concepts and practices* (3rd Ed.). Wadsworth Thomson Learning.
- McMinn, D. (n.d.). *Eleven ways to become a visionary leader.* Retrieved from <https://preachititeachit.org/articles/detail/11-ways-to-become-a-visionary-leader/>
- McTaggart, R. (1991). Principles for participatory action research. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 41(3), 168–187.
- McTaggart, R. (2010). *Participatory action research or change and development.* James Cook University.
- Meier, J.D. (n.d.). *Visionary leadership.* Retrieved from <http://sourcesofinsight.com/visionary-leadership/>
- Meinert, D. (2015, November 1). *How to be a visionary leader.* Retrieved from <https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/news/hr-magazine/pages/1115-execbrief.aspx>
- Mills, G. E. (2007). *Action research: A guide for the teacher researcher* (3rd Ed.). Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Northwest Executive Education. (2020). *6 Steps to Become a Visionary Leader.* Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3hC8A1e>
- Orr, M. (2018, May 15). *Five steps to becoming a visionary leader.* Retrieved from <https://www.capacitybc.com/5-steps-to-becoming-a-visionary-leader>
- Patulli, J.J. (2018, May). *Everyone can be a leader.* Retrieved from <https://www.hsdinstitute.org/resources/everyone-can-be-a-leader.html#:~:text=Everyone%20can%20be%20a%20leader.,around%20you%20to%20be%20successful>
- Phramaha Pajit Uttamadhammo (Sakhong) & Phrakrusutheejariyawattana. (2021). Development of Learning by E-Learning System: A Case of Mahamakut Buddhist University, Mahavajiralongkorn Rajavijayalaya Campus. *World Journal of Education*, 11(3), 47-59. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v11n3p47>
- Rooptam, S. & Sanrattana, W. (2021). Participatory Practice “Teach Less, Learn More”: A Case of Srikrananwittayakom School. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 4(2), 578-592. Retrieved from DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.302

- Rovinelli, R.J., & Hambleton, R.K. (1977). On the use of content specialists in the assessment of criterion-referenced test item validity. *Dutch Journal of Educational Research*, 2, 49-60.
- Sanrattana, W. (2018). *Research in educational administration: Concepts, practices and case studies* (4th Ed.). Thiphawisut.
- Sarapoom, C., & Phrakrudhammapissamai. (2021). Cooperative practices to enhance the quality of work integrated learning at Nong Khai Technical College. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 7(3), 387-400. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.12973/ijem.7.3.387>
- Setzer, R. (2014, August 27). *The 8 habits of a visionary leader*. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/20141027160825-312489779-the-8-habits-of-a-visionary-leader>
- Simons, G. & Abramms, B. (1996). *The questions of diversity: Reproducible assessment tools for organizations and individuals*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/333uObb>
- Status Net. (n.d.). *What is visionary leadership*. Retrieved from <https://status.net/articles/visionary-leadership/>
- Taylor, S. (2017, November 17). *How to be a visionary leader*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2017/11/17/how-to-be-a-visionary-leader/?sh=523a143d1a44>
- Team Technology. (n.d.). *Visionary leadership*. Retrieved from <https://www.teamtechnology.co.uk/leadership/styles/visionary/>
- Thawinwong, C. & Sanrattana, W. (2022). Teachers and participatory action research for developing learning environments. *World Journal of Education*, 12(3), 17-28. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v12n3p17>
- Turner, R. & Carlson, L.A. (2003). Indexes of item-objective congruence for multidimensional items. *International Journal of Testing*, 3(2):163-171. Retrieved from DOI:10.1207/S15327574IJT0302_5
- UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group. (2016, August 22). *What does Cronbach's alpha mean?* Retrieved from <https://stats.idre.ucla.edu/spss/faq/what-does-cronbachs-alpha-mean/>
- Williams, C. (n.d.). *Nine steps to help you become a visionary leader at work*. Retrieved from <https://www.lifecoachspotter.com/9-steps-to-help-you-become-a-visionary-leader-at-work/>
- Work Front. (2018, May 7). *Four ways to be a visionary leader in the digital age*. Retrieved from <https://www.workfront.com/blog/4-ways-to-be-a-visionary-leader-in-the-digital-age>
- Wroblewski, M.T. (2019, August 5). *Characteristics of visionary leadership*. Retrieved from <https://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/characteristics-visionary-leadership-9056.html>